

Anionic [4+2]cycloaddition — Retro[4+2]cycloaddition strategy in the synthesis of psoralen and its isoster[†]

Mausumi Bandyopadhyay, Kalyani Datta and Dipakranjan Mal*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302, India

Manuscript received 27 July 1999

Furan-1,4-dipolar agents **7** and **16c**, prepared in few steps from commercially available furoates, have been annulated with bicyclopentadienone **2** to provide pentacyclic frameworks **8** and **17** respectively. Subsequent transformations of **8** and **17** through retro-Diels-Alder reaction and indenol-indanone rearrangement have furnished psoralen precursors **14** and **19**. Similarly, oxaindacenone **23** has been prepared in good yield from **21**.

The linearly fused furocoumarins such as psoralen are well established photodynamic drugs, which are widely used in photochemotherapy for management of such skin diseases as psoriasis, vitiligo, eczema and mycosis fungoids¹. Of late, they are finding newer pharmaceutical uses. For instance, 8-methoxypsoralen (8-MOP), a prominent member of furocoumarin family, has been introduced as a clinically effective drug for the treatment of cutaneous T-cell lymphoma. 5-Methoxypsoralen has been found to have potential utility in the treatment of human immunodeficiency disease (AIDS). In view of the renewed interest in furocoumarins, the alternative synthetic routes² to this class of molecules continue to be developed. The majority of the synthetic approaches³ reported so far have involved stepwise elaboration of the two heterocyclic rings beginning from a central aromatic core unit.

Recently, we have reported a new and potentially general approach⁴ to the construction of psoralens and demonstrated its viability by the total synthesis of 8-methoxypsoralen **5**. This approach is based upon regioselective annulation of sulfoxide **1** (Scheme 1) onto bicyclopentadienone **2**, giving pentacyclic frame intermediate **3**. Flash vacuum

pyrolysis of this intermediate furnished the key indacenone **4**, which was subsequently transformed to 8-MOP **5** in two steps. We now report successful application of this protocol in the regioselective synthesis of psoralen **9** in which the central aromatic ring carries no substituent.

Results and Discussion

The retrosynthetic analysis of psoralen **9**, similar to that of **5**, called for the preparation of pentacyclic intermediate **8**. For the synthesis of the key intermediate **8**, it was decided to prepare furan derivative **6** or **7** having an aldehyde group at C-2, so that after annulation with **2**, it would incorporate no phenolic group in the central benzene ring. Between the two reagents, the choice was made in favor of **7**, with the apprehension that synthesis of **6** would be more problematic due to the presence of acid-sensitive sulfoxide functionality.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (a) ^tBuOLi, THF, (b) Me₂SO₄, K₂CO₃, acetone, (c) FVP.

Fig. 1

Preparation of the annulating agent 7: Commercially available furan-2-ester **10a** was converted to **7** (Scheme 2). NBS bromination of **10a** in CCl₄ provided **10b**⁴. Reaction of **10b** with sodium benzenesulfinate gave **10c** (80%). Alkaline hydrolysis of the ester furnished the corresponding acid **11** in 80% yield. It was then subjected to mixed anhydride formation with ethyl chloroformate, followed by sodium borohydride reduction to give alcohol **12** (60%). Oxidation of this alcohol with active manganese dioxide in dichloromethane yielded the required aldehyde **7** (65%).

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri in recognition of his outstanding contribution to organic chemistry.

Scheme 2. Reagents : (a) NBS, (b) PhSO₂Na⁺, (c) NaOH, EtOH, HCl, (d) ClCO₂Et, Et₃N, THF, NaBH₄, H₂O, (e) MnO₂, CH₂Cl₂.

The annulation of **7** with **2** was examined next (Scheme 3). It may be emphasized that success of the annulation, consisting of four steps (Michael addition, cyclization, elimination of H₂O and PhSO₃H) is highly dependent upon the nature of base, solvent and temperature of the reaction. No clear-cut guideline for this type of annulation can be

together with **15** in 35% yield. The thermolysis of **15** yielded indacenone **14** in almost quantitative yield. The formation of **14** from **13** can be explained by invoking retro-Diels-Alder reaction of **13**, followed by 1,5-sigmatropic H-migration and tautomerization. Since indacenone **14**⁷ has been reported to give psoralen **9** in two steps, this synthesis of oxaindacenone **14** constitutes a new regioselective synthesis of psoralen **9**.

Having successfully completed the synthesis of psoralen **9**, we sought to generalize the approach, i.e. anionic annulation – retro-Diels-Alder reaction – indenol-indanone rearrangement and decided to apply it to the synthesis of hitherto unreported psoralen isoster **20** (Scheme 4).

The required furan-1,4-dipolar synthon **16e** was prepared from the bromo derivative **16a**⁸ in four steps in the manner analogous to **7**. Treatment of **16a**⁸ with one equivalent of sodium benzenesulfinate in DMF afforded the sulfone **16b**

Scheme 3

derived from literature⁵. Initially, we employed potassium tert-butoxide in tert-butanol in the annulation, as this system was successful with a benzene derivative⁶. But the reaction provided a mixture of products which retained phenyl sulfonyl groups as revealed by IR and NMR data of the mixture, and no desired annulated product **8**. After several unsuccessful attempts of annulation of **7** with **2** using different base-solvent systems, it was found that sodium methoxide in methanol at 0° is the suitable condition for the annulation. Accordingly, the desired product **8** was obtained in 51% yield. The PMR spectrum of this product was fully consistent with the structure. It was further characterized by other spectroscopic means.

For the conversion of the annulated product **8** to oxaindacenone **14**, we utilized indenol-indanone rearrangement reported by us in a recent communication⁶. Accordingly, **8** was reduced with sodium borohydride to the corresponding alcohol **13** in 99% yield. On flash vacuum pyrolysis, **13** directly provided oxaindacenone **14** in 50% yield

(95%). Alkaline hydrolysis of **16b** afforded the acid **16c**. Sodium borohydride reduction of the acid **16c** through its mixed anhydride furnished the alcohol **16d** (60%), which was oxidized to the aldehyde **16e** in 60% yield by pyridinium chlorochromate. The aldehyde **16e** was then annulated with **2** under the condition (NaOMe, MeOH) proven for **7**, and the desired product **17** was obtained in 40% yield. Further transformation of **17** to the target oxaindacenone **19** proceeded through **18**. Sodium borohydride reduction of **17** furnished **18** (99%). Thermolytic decomposition of **18** provided **19** in 80% yield. Unfortunately, the ring expansion of cyclopentanone ring of **19** by Baeyer-Villiger oxidation could not be accomplished. It seems that furan 'O' sufficiently deactivates carbonyl carbon of cyclopentanone towards peracids. Though the completion of synthesis of the isoster **20** was not possible, we proceeded further to generalize the indenol-indanone rearrangement (i.e. **18** to **19**). Hence, the pentacyclic alcohol **22** was prepared from the ketone **21**⁴ by sodium borohydride reduction. X-Ray crystallographic

Scheme 4. Reagents : (a) PhSO₂Na⁺, (b) NaOH, HCl, (c) ClCO₂Et, NaBH₄, (d) PCC, (e) NaOMe, MeOH, (f) NaBH₄, EtOH, (g) diethylene glycol, heat.

analysis⁹ of the alcohol **20** supported the gross structure as well as the stereochemistry of the hydroxy group as shown in Scheme 5. Subsequent thermolysis of the alcohol **22** furnished the new oxindacenone **23** in 60% yield. Similar to **19**, Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of **23** under a variety of conditions failed. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that furan annulation – retro-Diels-Alder reaction – indenol-indanone rearrangement is a general methodology for the synthesis of oxindacenones.

Scheme 5. Reagents : (a) NaBH₄, EtOH, (b) diethylene glycol, heat.

Experimental

The general experimental procedure has been described in an earlier publication⁴.

3-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-2-furaldehyde (7) : To a stirred solution of the furfuryl alcohol **12** (0.5 g, 1.9 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (25 ml), active manganese dioxide (6.4 g, 29.7 mmol) was added. After overnight stirring, the mixture was filtered and washed with dichloromethane (5 × 5 ml). Then the filtrate and the washings were combined, concentrated and extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 10 ml). The organic phase was worked up in usual manner and column chromatographed to furnish the desired product **7** as white crystals (0.31 g, 65%), m.p. 93–94° (Found : C, 57.35; H, 3.97. C₁₂H₁₀O₄S calcd. for : C, 57.58; H, 4.02%); ν_{\max} 3428, 3127, 1679, 1478, 1385, 1302, 1237, 1140, 1081, 692 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 9.45 (1H, s, CHO), 7.75–7.71 (2H, m, ArH), 7.58 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.50–7.46 (2H, m, ArH), 6.81 (1H, s, furo-H), 4.65 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph); δ_{C} 178.8, 147.0, 134.0, 128.9, 128.4, 121.7, 115.3, 52.1; *m/z* 250 (M⁺), 232, 185, 168, 157, 141, 125, 109 (100%).

5a,5,8,8a-Tetrahydro-5,8-methanofluoreno[2,3-b]furan-9(9H)-one (8) : To a stirred solution of NaOMe (3 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) at room temperature the aldehyde **7** (0.5 g, 1 mmol) was added. The color of the solution immediately turned yellow. After 5–10 min, Michael acceptor **2** (0.35 g, 1.2 mmol) was added. The resulting mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 10 ml) and the combined phase washed with brine (2 × 5 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed (silica gel) to give **8** as light yellow crystals (0.12 g, 51%), m.p. 159–160° (Found : C, 81.27; H, 5.00. C₁₆H₁₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 81.34; H, 5.12%); ν_{\max} 2969, 1684, 1615, 1451, 1319, 1117, 1020, 877 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.74 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, furo-H), 7.67 (1H, s, ArH), 7.56 (1H, s, *J* 1.8 Hz, furo-H), 5.91–5.88 (1H, m, CH=), 5.46–5.44 (1H, m, CH=), 3.96–3.93 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.37 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, ring-H), 3.28–3.24 (2H, m, ring-H), 1.77 (2H, ABq, *J* 2 Hz, CH₂); δ_{13} 207.0, 154.0, 149.8, 148.0, 136.0, 134.0, 133.0, 117.0, 106.0, 105.0, 53.0, 52.0, 46.0, 45.0, 44.4, 44.3; *m/z* 236 (M⁺), 170 (100%), 142, 113, 66.

Methyl 3-(phenylsulfonylmethyl)-2-furoate (10c) : To a well stirred solution of compound **10b** (4.0 g, 18 mmol) in dry DMF (65 ml) was added solid sodium benzenesulfinate (7.5 g, 45 mmol) in portions. The mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature and then the resultant solidous mass diluted with cold water (600 ml). The white material precipitated was filtered and recrystallized (dichloromethane-hexane) to give shining yellowish crystals of **10c** (4 g, 80%), m.p. 111–112°; ν_{\max} 3419, 2937, 1712, 1431, 1306, 1139, 802 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.72–7.42 (5H, m, ArH), 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, furo-H), 7.59–7.55 (1H, m, ArH), 7.51–7.42 (3H, m, ArH), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.65 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 3.66 (3H, s, COOCH₃); δ_{13} 158.2, 145.1, 142.0, 138.0, 133.5, 128.6, 128.5, 121.8,

114.5, 52.9, 51.5; m/z 280 (M^+), 249, 184, 157, 139 (100%), 109.

3-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-2-furoic acid (11): An aqueous solution of NaOH (20%; 70 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the ester **10c** (5 g, 17.8 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml). After overnight stirring, much of ethanol was removed under reduced pressure. Then it was acidified with 6 N HCl (15 ml) at 0°. Dirty white precipitate formed was filtered, dried and purified by recrystallization from EtOH-H₂O to give **11** (3.8 g, 80%), m.p. 187–188° (Found: C, 53.95; H, 3.65. C₁₂H₁₀O₅S calcd. for: C, 54.12; H, 3.78%); ν_{\max} 3432, 2941, 1681, 1596, 1443, 1312, 1133, 1073, 891, 753 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.56 (1H, d, J 1.4 Hz, ArH), 7.54–7.52 (1H, m, furo-H), 7.43 (1H, dd, J 7.2, 8.2 Hz, ArH), 7.41 (1H, d, J 1 Hz, ArH), 7.35–7.27 (2H, m, J 2 Hz, ArH), 6.46 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.56 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 3.2 (1H, bs, COOH); δ_{13} 159.6, 144.9, 143.0, 137.8, 133.7, 128.8, 128.4, 120.8, 114.1, 52.9; m/z 266 (M^+), 222, 184, 157, 141, 125 (100%), 108, 81.

3-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-2-furfuryl alcohol (12): A solution of ethyl chloroformate (0.36 ml, 3.75 mmol) in dry THF (3 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the acid **11** (1 g, 3.7 mmol) and triethylamine (0.52 ml, 3.75 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) at –10 to –5°. After 1 h of stirring, precipitated triethylammonium chloride was filtered off and washed with dry THF (10 ml). Then the combined filtrate and washing was added during 30 min to a solution of sodium borohydride (0.36 g in 13.5 ml water) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for additional 3 h and then acidified with 6 N HCl (10 ml). The reaction mixture was extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 20 ml) and the combined organic phase was washed successively with NaHCO₃ (2 × 10 ml), water (2 × 10 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated. The column chromatography of the residue furnished **12** as a light yellow solid (0.57 g, 60%), m.p. 90–91°; ν_{\max} 3373, 2936, 1721, 1443, 1410, 1301, 1151, 1080, 1009, 740 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.78 (1H, d, J 1.4 Hz, ArH), 7.75 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.66–7.62 (1H, m, ArH), 7.57–7.49 (2H, m, ArH), 7.26 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz, ArH), 5.93 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.5 (2H, s, CH₂OH), 4.23 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 2.6 (1H, bs, CH₂OH); m/z 252 (M^+), 141, 125, 111 (100%), 83.

4b, 5, 8a, 9-Pentahydro-9-hydroxy-5,8-methano-fluoreno[2,3-b]furan (13): To a stirred solution of **8** (0.25 g, 1.05 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml), sodium borohydride (0.1 g, 2.6 mmol) was added in one portion. After overnight stirring, the solution was concentrated and water (5 ml) was added to the residue to give a solid. It was then filtered, dried under reduced pressure and recrystallized from EtOH-

H₂O to give **13** (~0.25 g, 99%), m.p. 87°; ν_{\max} 3502, 2973, 2887, 1446, 1339, 1312, 1030, 860, 764, 727 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.56 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.36 (1H, s, ArH), 7.29 (1H, s, ArH), 6.67 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.04–6.01 (1H, m, CH=), 5.51–5.48 (1H, m, =CH), 5.24 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, CH-OH), 3.92–3.87 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.35–3.25 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.22 (1H, bs, ring-H), 3.12 (1H, bs, ring-H), 1.65–1.58 (2H, m, CH₂); δ_{13} 145.4, 144.4, 138.8, 135.7, 133.4, 128.1, 115.7, 106.8, 74.7, 48.2, 49.4, 50.7, 51.8, 44.5; m/z 238 (M^+), 220, 205, 189, 172 (100%), 144, 155, 115.

5,6-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-1-oxa-s-indacene-7-one (14): Compound **13** was pyrolysed (450–475°) under FVP condition⁴ described earlier to furnish two compounds **14** and **15**: **14** (light yellow, 50%), m.p. 145° (lit.⁷ 146°); ν_{\max} 3261, 1448, 1367, 1315, 1105, 1055, 962, 839 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.64 (1H, s, ArH), 7.60 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.37 (1H, s, ArH), 6.77 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, benzylic-H), 6.73 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.38 (1H, dd, J 6 Hz, CHCHOH), 5.22 (1H, bd, J 8 Hz, CHOH), 1.54 (1H, bs, OH); **15** (white, 35%), m.p. 108°; ν_{\max} 2926, 1693, 1611, 1439, 1312, 1263, 856, 772 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.85 (1H, s, ArH), 7.77 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.61 (1H, s, ArH), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 3.25–3.19 (2H, m, COCH₂), 2.81–2.75 (2H, m, COCH₂CH₂); m/z 172 (M^+ , 100%), 155, 144, 115.

Methyl 2-(phenylsulfonylmethyl)-3-furoate (16b): This white colored compound was prepared in 95% yield from **16a**, following the procedure described for **10c**: m.p. 91–92°; ν_{\max} 2996, 1712, 1612, 1442, 1320, 1209, 1157, 1050, 758 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.72 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, ArH), 7.69 (1H, t, J 2, 4 Hz, ArH), 7.51 (1H, t, J 1.8, 3.2 Hz, ArH), 7.47 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, ArH), 7.40 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.63 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.84 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 3.60 (3H, s, COOCH₃); δ_{13} 162.5, 147.7, 143.5, 138.1, 133.7, 128.7, 128.4, 118.3, 111.1, 54.7, 51.4; m/z 280 (M^+), 249, 201, 184, 157, 139 (100%), 109, 77.

2-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-3-furoic acid (16c): This white colored compound was prepared in 90% yield from **16b** according to the procedure given for **11**; m.p. 159–160° (Found: C, 53.85; H, 3.69. C₁₂H₁₀O₅S calcd. for: C, 54.12; H, 3.78%); ν_{\max} 3005, 2940, 1681, 1598, 1323, 1273, 1158, 758 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.76–7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 7.43 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.70 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.85 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 3.09 (1H, bs, CO₂H); δ_{13} 164.0, 147.5, 143.4, 138.2, 133.8, 128.9, 128.3, 119.3, 111.6, 54.6; m/z 266 (M^+), 184, 157, 142, 125 (100%), 97, 77.

2-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-3-furfuryl alcohol (16d): It was prepared in 60% as an oil from **16c**, according to the procedure given for **12**: ν_{\max} 3502, 2921, 1299, 1153, 1066, 1019, 757 cm⁻¹; δ_H 7.71–7.46 (5H, m, ArH), 7.14 (1H, d,

J 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.37 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, furo-H), 4.49 (2H, s, CH₂OH), 4.47 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph), 2.71 (1H, bs, CH₂OH); δ_{13} 143.0, 138.9, 133.7, 129.0, 128.4, 126.7, 111.9, 96.1, 55.9, 54.6.

2-(Phenylsulfonylmethyl)-3-furaldehyde (16e) : To a stirred solution of the furfuryl alcohol **16d** (0.5 g, 1.9 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (25 ml); pyridinium chlorochromate (6.4 g, 29.7 mmol) was added. After overnight stirring, the mixture was filtered and washed with CH₂Cl₂ (5 × 5 ml). Then the filtrate was concentrated, poured in water (50 ml) and extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 10 ml). The organic phase was worked up in usual manner and chromatographed to furnish **16e** (0.29 g, 60%) m.p. 106–107° (Found : C, 57.52; H, 3.92. C₁₂H₁₀O₄S calcd. for : C, 57.58; H, 4.02%); ν_{\max} 3154, 2926, 1680, 1315, 1233, 1172, 1132, 1083, 751 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 9.59 (1H, s, CHO), 7.74–7.49 (5H, m, ArH), 7.38 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.71 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.74 (2H, s, CH₂SO₂Ph); δ_{13} 183.1, 149.0, 144.2, 137.9, 134.0, 128.7, 126.0, 109.4, 96.0, 54.6; *m/z* 250 (M⁺), 185, 157, 141, 109 (100%).

6a, 6, 9, 9a-Tetrahydro-6, 9-methanofluoreno[2, 3-b]furan-5(5H)-one (17) : This white colored compound was prepared in 40% yield from **16e** and **2** by the procedure adopted for compound **8**; m.p. 70° (Found : C, 81.02; H, 5.06. C₁₆H₁₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 81.34; H, 5.12%); ν_{\max} 3095, 2961, 1681, 1326, 1298, 1113, 1018, 890, 722 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.8 (1H, s, ArH), 7.63 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.46 (1H, s, ArH), 6.79 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 5.92–5.88 (1H, m, CH=), 5.48–5.44 (1H, m, =CH), 3.99–3.93 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.37 (1H, d, *J* 4 Hz, ring-H), 3.28–3.22 (2H, m, ring-H), 1.77 (2H, ABq, *J* 2 Hz, CH₂); δ_{13} 206.3, 159.2, 152.4, 146.3, 135.7, 133.4, 127.7, 116.4, 107.9, 107.3, 107.2, 53.4, 52.6, 46.0, 45.5, 44.6; *m/z* 236 (M⁺), 221, 208, 170 (100%), 142, 114.

5, 5a, 6, 9, 9a-Pentahydro-5-hydroxy-6, 9-methanofluoreno[2, 3-d]furan (18) : Reduction of **17** to **18** (99%) was performed according to the procedure followed for **13** : m.p. 100°; ν_{\max} 3515, 2954, 1329, 1147, 1060, 859, 736 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.54 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.43 (1H, s, ArH), 7.21 (1H, s, ArH), 6.69 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.04–6.00 (1H, m, CH=), 5.53–5.49 (1H, m, =CH), 5.23 (1H, t, *J* 8, 18 Hz, CHOH), 3.94–3.88 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.35–3.26 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.24–3.22 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.12 (1H, bs, ring-H), 1.64–1.59 (2H, m, CH₂); δ_{13} 155.6, 144.9, 142.4, 141.1, 135.4, 133.5, 126.9, 116.3, 106.5, 106.4, 74.4, 51.7, 51.0, 49.3, 48.1, 44.9; *m/z* 238 (M⁺), 220, 205, 191, 172 (100%), 155, 144, 115.

6, 7-Dihydro-1-oxa-s-indacen-5-one (19) : Compound **18** (0.1 g, 0.42 mmol) was heated at reflux in diethylene glycol (5 ml) for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water (15 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 ml). After usual work-up of the organic extract, the resulting residue was chromatographed to give **19** (0.05 g, 80%), m.p. 158°; ν_{\max} 3133, 2927, 1697, 1282, 1096, 1004, 867, 760 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 8.01 (1H, s, ArH), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.53 (1H, s, ArH), 7.84 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 3.28–3.22 (2H, m, COCH₂), 2.81–2.75 (2H, m, COCH₂CH₂); δ_{13} 206.1, 159.5, 151.5, 146.5, 132.8, 127.8, 116.8, 108.7, 107.3, 36.8, 25.6; *m/z* 172 (M⁺), 144 (100%), 115, 89, 63.

5, 5a, 6, 9, 9a-Pentahydro-5-hydroxy-6, 9-methano-4-methoxyfluoreno[3, 2-b]furan (22) : It was prepared in 99% yield from **21** according to the procedure given for **13** : m.p. 117–118°; ν_{\max} 3525, 3112, 2953, 1598, 1459, 1338, 1240, 1069, 737 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.44 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 6.87 (1H, s, ArH), 6.84–6.82 (1H, m, furo-H), 6.04–6.007 (1H, m, =CH), 5.43–5.33 (2H, m, =CH, CHOH), 4.14 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.84–3.77 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.30–3.24 (1H, m, ring-H), 3.15–3.13 (2H, m, ring-H), 1.62–1.50 (1H, ABq, *J* 8, 14 Hz, CH₂), 2.37 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, CHOH); δ_{13} 158.0, 148.9, 143.4, 143.0, 135.3, 133.0, 129.5, 115.4, 104.7, 100.6, 72.6, 58.9, 51.5, 51.4, 48.6, 47.6, 44.9; *m/z* 268 (M⁺), 250, 202 (100%), 185, 170, 165.

6, 7-Dihydro-4-methoxy-1-oxa-s-indacen-5-one (23) : It was prepared in 60% yield from **22** following the procedure described for **19** from **18** : m.p. 110–111° (Found : C, 71.15; H, 4.90. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ calcd. for : C, 71.27; H, 4.98%); ν_{\max} 3498, 3100, 2932, 1674, 1595, 1457, 1322, 1087 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 7.18 (1H, s, ArH), 6.99 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, furo-H), 4.27 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.20–3.14 (2H, m, COCH₂), 2.75–2.69 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂); δ_{13} 203.5, 161.5, 153.4, 152.6, 144.3, 121.2, 16.8, 105.9, 102.8, 60.4, 37.4, 25.3; *m/z* 202 (M⁺), 173 (100%), 144, 131, 115, 102.

Acknowledgement

Financial support was provided by C.S.I.R., New Delhi. The authors are thankful to Dr. K. V. S. N. Murty of Switzerland for providing spectral data.

References

- 1 R M Knobler, H Homigsmann and R L Edelson, 'Psoralen Phototherapies', in "Psoralen DNA Photobiology", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1988, Vol II, pp 117-134
- 2 (a) R L Danheiser and M P Trova, *Synlett*, 1995, 573, (b) A E Jacokbs and L Christiaens, *J Org Chem*, 1996, 61, 4842,

- (c) E. Zubia, F. R. Luiss, G. M. Massanet and I. G. Collado, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 4239; (d) B. M. Aquila, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 2795.
3. E. J. Bisagni, *Photochem. Photobiol. B : Biol.*, 1992, **14**, 23.
 4. D. Mal, M. Bandyopadhyay, K. Datta and K. V. S. N. Murty, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **54**, 7525.
 5. S. K. Ghorai, H. N. Roy, M. Bandyopadhyay and D. Mal, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1999, 30.
 6. S. K. Ghorai, N. K. Hazra and D. Mal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **39**, 689.
 7. K. Hayakawa, M. Yodo, S. Ohsuki and K. Kanematsu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 6735.
 8. J. D. Prugh, A. C. Huitric and W. C. McCarthy, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 1991.
 9. K. Chinnakali, H. -K. Fun, D. Mal, M. Bandyopadhyay, K. Datta and D. Nigam, *Acta Crystallogr. , Ser. C*, 1999, **55**, 774.